

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

EQUIVARIANT FIBER RESOLUTIONS OF CONTINUOUS MAPS

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Abstract

The shape theory of continuous maps is a new branch of classical shape theory and is an extension of the homotopy theory of absolute neighborhood retracts for the category of maps of metrizable spaces. In this paper we investigate equivariant fiber resolution of a map in the equivariant homotopy category of G -maps.

Keywords and Phrases: G -map, equivariant fiber resolution of a G -map, equivariant fiber expansion of the G -map.

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Equivariant Fiber Resolutions of Continuous Maps. Let $f = \{f_\mu, (p_\mu, p'_\mu), M\}$ is an inverse system of the category $\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G}$ and let (f) be a rudimentary system whose term is only a G -map $f: X \rightarrow X'$ of a category \mathbf{Top}_G .

Definition 1. An equivariant fiber resolution of a G -map f is a morphism $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') = \{(p_\mu, p'_\mu), \mu \in M\} : (f) \rightarrow \mathbf{f}$ of the category $\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G}$ which for any $G - \mathbf{ANR}(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -map $t: P \rightarrow P'$ and a pair (α, α') of coverings $\alpha \in \mathbf{Cov}(P)$ and $\alpha' \in \mathbf{Cov}(P')$ satisfies the following two conditions:

EFR1) for every morphism $(\varphi, \varphi'): f \rightarrow t$ there exist $\mu \in M$ and a morphism $(\varphi_\mu, \varphi'_\mu): f_\mu \rightarrow t$ such that $(\varphi_\mu, \varphi'_\mu) \cdot (p_\mu, p'_\mu)$ and (φ, φ') are (α, α') -near;

EFR2) there exist a pair (β, β') of coverings $\beta \in \mathbf{Cov}(P)$ and $\beta' \in \mathbf{Cov}(P')$ with the following property, if $\mu \in M$ and $(\varphi_\mu, \varphi'_\mu), (\psi_\mu, \psi'_\mu): f_\mu \rightarrow t$ are morphisms such that the morphisms $(\varphi_\mu, \varphi'_\mu) \cdot (p_\mu, p'_\mu)$ and $(\psi_\mu, \psi'_\mu) \cdot (p_\mu, p'_\mu)$ are (β, β') -near, then there exists a $\mu' \geq \mu$ such that $(\varphi_{\mu'}, \varphi'_{\mu'}) \cdot (p_{\mu'}, p'_{\mu'})$ and $(\psi_{\mu'}, \psi'_{\mu'}) \cdot (p_{\mu'}, p'_{\mu'})$ are (α, α') -near.

If in a equivariant fiber resolution $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') : (f) \rightarrow \mathbf{f}$ all f_μ are $G - \mathbf{ANR}(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -maps, then $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')$ is an $\mathbf{ANR}_G(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -fiber resolution.

Theorem 2. Every G -map $f: X \rightarrow X'$ of topological G -spaces admits an $\mathbf{ANR}_G(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -fiber resolution.

Proof. Let $t: P \rightarrow P'$ and $t_1: P_1 \rightarrow P'_1$ be the G -maps and let $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') : f \rightarrow t$

and $(\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}'_1) : f \rightarrow t_1$ be the morphisms. We say that $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')$ and $(\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}'_1)$ are G -equivalent if there exists an isomorphism $(\varphi, \varphi'): t \rightarrow t_1$ such that $(\varphi, \varphi') \cdot (\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') = (\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}'_1)$.

Let \mathbb{I} consist of all equivalence classes of the morphism $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') : f \rightarrow t$, where t is a G -map with weight $\omega(t) \leq \max\{w(f), \aleph_0\} = \tau$. \mathbb{I} is a set because every such map t we can embed in the projection $\pi: I^\tau \rightarrow I^\tau$, where I^τ is a Tychonoff cube of weight τ . For every $\gamma \in \mathbb{I}$ consider a morphism $(\mathbf{p}_\gamma, \mathbf{p}'_\gamma) : f \rightarrow t_\gamma$, where t_γ is a $\mathbf{ANR}_G(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -map such that $w(t_\gamma) \leq \gamma$.

Let Δ be a set of finite subsets

$$\delta = \{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n\} \leq \delta' = \{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n, \gamma_{n+1}, \dots, \gamma_m\}.$$

We define the morphism $(\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta'}) : t_{\delta'} = t_{\gamma_1} \times t_{\gamma_2} \times \dots \times t_{\gamma_n} \times t_{\gamma_{n+1}} \times \dots \times t_{\gamma_m} \rightarrow t_\delta = t_{\gamma_1} \times t_{\gamma_2} \times \dots \times t_{\gamma_n}$ as the pair of G -projections. It is clear, that for every $\delta \leq \delta' \leq \delta''$

$$(\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta'}) \cdot (\mathbf{p}_{\delta'\delta''}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta'\delta''}) = (\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta''}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta''})$$

and for any $\delta \in \Delta$, t_δ is a $\mathbf{ANR}_G(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -map. Obviously, $\mathbf{t} = \{t_\delta, (\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta'}), \Delta\}$ is a $G - \mathbf{ANR}(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$ -inverse system.

Now we define the morphism $(\mathbf{p}_\delta, \mathbf{p}'_\delta) : f \rightarrow t_\delta$. It is a pair $(p_{\gamma_1} \times p_{\gamma_2} \times \dots \times p_{\gamma_n}, p'_{\gamma_1} \times p'_{\gamma_2} \times \dots \times p'_{\gamma_n})$. The family $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') = \{(\mathbf{p}_\delta, \mathbf{p}'_\delta), \delta \in \Delta\}$ is a morphism of $\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{Mor}_{G - \mathbf{Top}}$.

It is readily seen that $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')$ has a property EFR1). Therefore we can replace the inverse system \mathbf{t} by a larger inverse system. Let $\Lambda = \{\lambda = (\delta, h)\}$, where $\delta \in \Delta$ and h is a G -neighborhood of the G -map $t_{\delta|p_\delta(X)} : p_\delta(X) \rightarrow p_\delta(X')$ in t_δ . Let, $f_\lambda = h$. Obviously, $f_\lambda \in \mathbf{ANR}_G(\mathbf{Mor}_M)$. We order Λ by putting $\lambda = (\delta, h) \leq \lambda' = (\delta', h')$ if and only if $\delta \leq \delta'$ and $(\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta'}) \cdot (h')$ is a submap of h . Now we define a morphism $(\mathbf{p}_{\lambda\lambda'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\lambda\lambda'}) : f_{\lambda'} \rightarrow f_\lambda$ as a restriction of the morphism $(\mathbf{p}_{\delta\delta'}, \mathbf{p}'_{\delta\delta'})$ on h' . Let $p_\lambda = p_\delta : f \rightarrow h$ for every $\lambda = (\delta, h) \in \Lambda$. It is clear we have

a $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –inverse system $\mathbf{f} = \{f_\lambda, (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}), \Lambda\}$. Obviously, the morphism $\{(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda), \lambda \in \Lambda\}: (f) \rightarrow \mathbf{f}$ of the category $\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G}$ has property EFR1).

Now we check that $\{(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda), \lambda \in \Lambda\}: (f) \rightarrow \mathbf{f}$ satisfies condition EFR2). Let $\lambda = (\delta, h)$ be an index of Λ , where $h: C \rightarrow Q$ is a G -map. Let $(\varphi, \varphi'), (\psi, \psi'): h \rightarrow t$ be morphisms such that $(\varphi, \varphi') \cdot (p_\delta, p'_\delta)$ and $(\psi, \psi') \cdot (p_\delta, p'_\delta)$ are (α, α') -near. For every point $y \in p_\delta(X)$ there exists a set $V \in \alpha$ such that $\varphi(y), \psi(y) \in V$. Moreover, there exists a neighborhood O_y of y such that $\varphi(O_y), \psi(O_y) \subset V$. Let $O = \bigcup_{y \in p_\delta(X)} O_y$. The set O is open in X_δ and $p_\delta(X) \subset O \subset C$. Equivariant restrictions $\varphi|_O$ and $\psi|_O$ are the are α –near

G -maps. Similarly, we conclude that there is an open set O' of $X_{\delta'}$ such that $p'_{\delta'}(X') \subset O' \subset Q$ and $\varphi'|_{O'}$ and $\psi'|_{O'}$ are the are α' –near G - maps.

Let $t_\delta^{-1}(O') \cap O = O''$. It is clear that $t_\delta(O'') \subset O'$. Consequently, $\lambda' = (\delta, t_\delta|_{O''}) \in \Lambda$ and $\lambda \leq \lambda'$. Hence, $(\varphi, \varphi') \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'})$ and $(\psi, \psi') \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'})$ are (α, α') -near.

Lemma 3. Let $p: E \rightarrow B$ be a topological G -space and let $r': P' \rightarrow Q'$ and $r: P \rightarrow Q$ be $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –maps. Let $(f, f_1): p \rightarrow r'$ and $(h_0, h_0'), (h_1, h_1'): r' \rightarrow r$ be morphisms such that $(h_0, h_0') \cdot (f, f_1)$ and $(h_1, h_1') \cdot (f, f_1)$ are G -homotopic. Then there exists a $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –map $r'': P'' \rightarrow Q''$ and morphisms $(f', f'_1): p \rightarrow r''$ and $(h, h'): r'' \rightarrow r'$ such that $(f, f_1) = (h, h') \cdot (f', f'_1) \cdot (h_0, h_0') \cdot (h, h') \simeq_G (h_1, h_1') \cdot (h, h')$.

The proof is similar of general case ([5]lemma 3.4.)

Definition 4. Let $f: X \rightarrow X'$ be a G -map of topological G -spaces, $[\mathbf{f}] = \{f_\lambda, [(p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'})], \Lambda\}$ be an inverse system in $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G})$ and $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')]: f \rightarrow [\mathbf{f}]$ be a morphism of $\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{pro} - \mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G})$. We call $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')]$ an equivariant fiber expansion of the G -map f , provided it has the following properties:

FE1) for every $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ map $t: P \rightarrow P'$ and a morphism $(\varphi, \varphi'): f \rightarrow t$ there is an index $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and a morphism $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda): f_\lambda \rightarrow t$ such that $(\varphi, \varphi') \simeq_G (\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$;

FE2) $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda), (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda): f_\lambda \rightarrow t$ are mophisms into a $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map $t: P \rightarrow P'$ and $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda) \simeq_G (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$, then there exists an index $\lambda' \geq \lambda$ such that $(\varphi, \varphi') \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}) \simeq_G (\psi, \psi') \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'})$.

If all $f_\lambda \in G - ANR(Mor_M)$, then $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')]: f \rightarrow [\mathbf{f}]$ is called $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ -fiber expansion.

Theorem 5. If $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}'): f \rightarrow \mathbf{f}$ is a equivariant fiber resolution of a G -map $: X \rightarrow X'$, then $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')]: f \rightarrow [\mathbf{f}]$ is an equivariant fiber expansion.

Proof. Let $t: P \rightarrow P'$ be an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map and let $(\varphi, \varphi'): f \rightarrow t$ be a morphism. Consider a pair (α, α') - of a $\alpha \in Cov(P)$ and $\alpha' \in Cov(P')$ such that (α, α') -near morphisms into t are G -homotopic. By the condition EFR1), there exist $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and a morphism $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda): f_\lambda \rightarrow t$ such that $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$ and (φ, φ') are (α, α') -near. Consequently, $(\varphi, \varphi') \simeq_G (\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$. It means $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')]$ has property FE1)

Let $t: P \rightarrow P'$ be an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map and let $\lambda \in \Lambda$ and $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda), (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda): f_\lambda \rightarrow t$ be the morphisms such that

$$(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda) \simeq_G (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda).$$

Let (α, α') be a pair of $\alpha \in Cov(P)$ and $\alpha' \in Cov(P')$ such that any (α, α') -near morphisms into t are G -homotopic. Choose a pair (β, β') of coverings $\beta \in Cov(P)$ and $\beta' \in Cov(P')$ according to EFR2). Let t be the map $t \times t$. Denote by $(v, v'): f \rightarrow t'$ a morphism defined by

$$\begin{aligned} v(x) &= (\varphi_\lambda p_\lambda(x), \psi_\lambda p_\lambda(x), x \in X, \\ v'(x') &= (\varphi'_\lambda p'_\lambda(x), \psi'_\lambda p'_\lambda(x'), x' \in X' \end{aligned}$$

Let (η, η') and (ξ, ξ') be the morphisms defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(y, y') &= y, \xi(y, y') = y', (y, y') \in P \times P, \\ \eta'(y_1, y'_1) &= y_1, \xi'(y_1, y'_1) = y'_1, (y_1, y'_1) \in P' \times P'. \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that $(\eta, \eta') \cdot (v, v') \simeq_G (\xi, \xi') \cdot (v, v')$. The G -map t' is an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map. By Lemma 3, there are an $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –map $t'': P'' \rightarrow P_1''$ and morphisms $(\sigma, \sigma'): f \rightarrow t'', (s_2, s'_2): t'' \rightarrow t'$ such that

$$(s_2, s'_2) \cdot (\sigma, \sigma') = (v, v'), (\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \simeq_G (\xi, \xi') \cdot (s_2, s'_2).$$

Let (β_1, β'_1) be a pair of equivariant coverings such that

$$\begin{aligned} \beta'_1 &> (\eta' \cdot s'_2)^{-1}(\beta') \wedge (\xi' \cdot s'_2)^{-1}(\beta'), \\ \beta_1 &> (\eta \cdot s_2)^{-1}(\beta) \wedge (\xi \cdot s_2)^{-1}(\beta) \wedge (t'')^{-1}(\beta'_1). \end{aligned}$$

By EFR1), there exist $\lambda'' \in \Lambda$ and $(o, o_1): f_{\lambda''} \rightarrow t''$ such that $\lambda'' \geq \lambda$ and (σ, σ') and $(o, o_1) \cdot (p_{\lambda''}, p'_{\lambda''})$ are the (β_1, β'_1) -near morphisms. Moreover,

$$(\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (\sigma, \sigma') = (\eta, \eta') \cdot (v, v') = (\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$$

implies that $(\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (o, o_1) \cdot (p_{\lambda''}, p'_{\lambda''})$ and $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda''}, p'_{\lambda\lambda''}) \cdot (p_{\lambda''}, p'_{\lambda''})$ are (β_1, β'_1) -near morphisms.. Consequently, there is a $\lambda''' \geq \lambda''$ such that

$$(\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (o, o_1) \cdot (p_{\lambda''\lambda'''}, p'_{\lambda''\lambda'''}) \text{ and } (\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda''''}, p'_{\lambda\lambda''''}) \text{ are the } (\alpha, \alpha')\text{-near morphisms and they are } G\text{-homotopic.}$$

Consequently there is a $\lambda'''' \geq \lambda'''$ such that

$$(\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (o, o_1) \cdot (p_{\lambda''\lambda''''}, p'_{\lambda''\lambda''''}) \simeq_G (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda''''}, p'_{\lambda\lambda''''}).$$

Let $\lambda' \geq \lambda''', \lambda''''$. It is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}) &\simeq_G (\eta, \eta') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (o, o_1) \cdot (p_{\lambda''\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda''\lambda'}) \simeq_G (\xi, \xi') \cdot (s_2, s'_2) \cdot (o, o_1) \cdot \\ (p_{\lambda''\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda''\lambda'}) &\simeq_G (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. Let $\pi : M \rightarrow M'$ be an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map and let $f : X \rightarrow X'$ be a closed submap of π . Let $\mathbf{f} = \{f_\lambda, (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}), \Lambda\}$ be the inverse system which consists of all neighborhoods $f_\lambda : U_\lambda \rightarrow U'_\lambda$ of f in π and embedding morphisms $(p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}) : f_{\lambda'} \rightarrow f_\lambda$ for every $\lambda \leq \lambda'$. Then the family $\{(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda), \lambda \in \Lambda\}$ consisting of equivariant embeddings $(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda) : f \rightarrow f_\lambda$ is the $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –fiber resolution.

Proof. Let $t : P \rightarrow P'$ be an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map, $(\varphi, \varphi') : f \rightarrow t$ be a morphism and (α, α') be a pair of a $\alpha \in Cov(P)$ and $\alpha' \in Cov(P')$. The map t is an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –map because there exist a neighborhood $h : C \rightarrow C'$ of a map f in π and an equivariant extension $(\tilde{\varphi}, \tilde{\varphi}') : h \rightarrow t$ of a morphism (φ, φ') . Let λ be the index such that $f_\lambda = h, U_\lambda = C$ and $U'_\lambda = C'$. Note that $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda) = (\varphi, \varphi')$ where $\varphi_\lambda = \tilde{\varphi}, \varphi'_\lambda = \tilde{\varphi}', p_\lambda = i : X \rightarrow C, p'_\lambda = i' : X' \rightarrow C'$. Consequently, (φ, φ') and $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$ are the (α, α') –near morphisms.

Let $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda), (\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) : f_\lambda \rightarrow t$ be the morphisms such that $(\varphi_\lambda, \varphi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$ and $(\psi_\lambda, \psi'_\lambda) \cdot (p_\lambda, p'_\lambda)$ are the (α, α') –near morphisms. For every point $y \in p_\lambda(X)$ there exists a equivariant $V \in \alpha$ of $\varphi_\lambda(y)$ such that $\varphi_\lambda(y) \in V$. By the continuity of φ_λ and ψ_λ we conclude that there is an equivariant neighborhood O_y of y in U_λ such that $\varphi_\lambda(O_y), \psi_\lambda(O_y) \subset V$. Let $\tilde{O} = \cup_{y \in p_\lambda(X)} O_y$. It is clear that \tilde{O} is open in U_λ , and $p_\lambda(X) \subset \tilde{O} \subset U_\lambda$. The maps $\varphi_\lambda|_{\tilde{O}}$ and $\psi_\lambda|_{\tilde{O}}$ are α –near.

Similarly, we conclude that there is an open set O' of U' such that $p'_\lambda(X') \subset O' \subset U'_\lambda$, and the maps $\varphi'_\lambda|_{O'}$ and $\psi'_\lambda|_{O'}$ are the α' –near maps.

Let $f_\lambda^{-1}(O') \cap \tilde{O} = O$. The equivariant restriction $f_\lambda|_O : O \rightarrow O'$ is an $G - ANR(Mor_M)$ –map. It is a neighborhood of f in π and a equivariant submap of f_λ . Let λ' be an index in Λ such that $f_{\lambda'} = f_\lambda|_O, U_{\lambda'} = O$ and $U'_{\lambda'} = O'$. Note that $f_{\lambda'} \in \mathbf{f}, \lambda' \geq \lambda$ and $(\varphi_{\lambda'}, \varphi'_{\lambda'}) \cdot (p_{\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda'})$ and $(\psi_{\lambda'}, \psi'_{\lambda'}) \cdot (p_{\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda'})$ are the (α, α') –near morphisms.

Any G –map $f : X \rightarrow X'$ of metric G –spaces can be considered as a closed submap of an $G - ANE(Mor_M)$ –map $\pi : M \rightarrow M'$. Consequently,

$$(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}') = \{(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda), \lambda \in \Lambda\} : f \rightarrow \mathbf{f} = \{f_\lambda, (p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}), \Lambda\},$$

where f_λ is an equivariant neighborhood of f in π , $(p_{\lambda\lambda'}, p'_{\lambda\lambda'}) : f_{\lambda'} \rightarrow f_\lambda$ is an equivariant embedding of $f_{\lambda'}$ in f_λ and $(p_\lambda, p'_\lambda) : f \rightarrow f_\lambda$ is an equivariant closed embedding of f in f_λ , is an $ANR_G(Mor_M)$ –fiber resolution and therefore $[(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}')] : f \rightarrow [\mathbf{f}]$ is an equivariant fiber expansion.

Now we have following main

Theorem 7. The category $H(ANR_G(Mor_M))$ is a dense subcategory of the category $H(\mathbf{Mor}_{\mathbf{Top}_G})$.

References

1. S. A. Antonian and S. Mardešić, Equivariant shape. Fund. Math., 127 (1987), 213–224.
2. A. Dold, The fixed index of fibr-preserving maps. Invent. Math., 25(1974), 281–298.
3. V. Baladze, On shape theory for fibrations, Bull. Georgian Acad. Sci., 129(1988), 269–272.
4. V. Baladze, Fiber shape theory and resolutions, Zb. Rad. Filoz. Fak. Nisu, Ser. Mat., 5(1991), 97–107.
5. V. Baladze, Fiber shape theory, Proc. A. Razmadze Math. Inst., 132(2003), 1–70.
6. V. Baladze; M. Dzadzamia . On retracts of compact transformation groups. Bull. Georgian Acad. Sci. 166, No2, 217–221 (2002).
7. M. Dzadzamia. Equivariant Fiber Retracts and Extensors of \mathbf{G} –maps. WSPÓŁPRACA EUROPEJSKA - cfmconsulting.pl. 6 (37), 9–20. (2018).
8. P. S. Gevorgyan, Generalized shape theory and movability of continuous transformation groups, Dissertation, MSU, 2001.
9. G.S. Ungar, ANR's and NES's in the category of mapping of matric spaces. Fund. Math. 95(1977), 111–127.